

STUDIES ON ADSORPTION IN RELATION TO CONSTITUTION. PART III. ADSORPTION OF CARBOHYDRATES FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS BY CHARCOAL

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Adsorption of a large number of carbohydrates by charcoal from aqueous solution has been studied. The adsorption constants have been shown to be distinctive of the different families of sugars. A comparison of the adsorption data with physical and chemical properties of the molecules has been made to throw some light on the nature of attachment of the solute to the solid adsorbent.

Occasional observations on adsorption of sugars by charcoal have been recorded since over a century (Wallace, *Pol. J.*, 1871, 201, 159; Mott, *Ber.*, 1880, 13, 1147; Morton, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 36, 1832). An examination of the literature, however, shows that the different carbohydrates have never been studied as regards their adsorption under similar conditions, and no attempts have been made to trace any connection between the constitution of the sugars and their adsorption. In the present investigation the general features governing the adsorption of carbohydrates under comparable conditions have been studied and an attempt has been made to correlate adsorption with the constitution of the carbohydrates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ten simpler saccharides, viz. arabinose, dextrose, galactose, laevulose, maltose, mannose, raffinose, rhamnose, sucrose and xylose were studied. A sample of Merck's animal charcoal, with an ash of 1.5% showed good adsorptive capacity and was used as the adsorbent in these experiments. Stock solutions (M/25) were prepared and diluted to different concentrations as required.

The method adopted for the estimation of the carbohydrates was one of direct weighing. Shallow cups of aluminium foil, 6 cm. x 4 cm. x 1 cm. were prepared, weighing about 0.3 g. each and were numbered. They were placed inside a small electrically heated oven and 5 c.c. of the experimental solution introduced into them. The temperature was then raised but was not allowed to exceed 60°. When the water had all evaporated, which took about 3 to 4 hours, the heating was continued for another half an hour (at 100° for hydrated sugars), after which the cups were withdrawn and immediately weighed. Preliminary experiments with known solutions showed that the estimations were correct to within 1% in the case of most of the sugars and to within 2% in the case of hydrated sugars.

The charcoal, previous to use, was heated to 200° under vacuum; 20 c.c. of the experimental solution were taken in each experiment, in well stoppered bottles with 2 g. of the charcoal and were maintained at 30° in a thermostat with occasional shaking for 72 hours. After the end of the experiment the solution was centrifuged and the clear solution was analysed. No filter papers were used. The experimental results are recorded in Tables I and II. Except where otherwise stated all concentrations are expressed as gram mols ($\times 10^5$).

The adsorption of some more carbohydrates was also studied under similar conditions, and the results are recorded in Table II. The concentrations are in g. per 5 c.c.

TABLE I

Arabinose.					Xylose.					Dextrose.				
Initial conc.	Equil. conc.	x/m .	Log c .	Log x/m .	Initial conc.	Equil. conc.	x/m .	Log c .	Log x/m .	Initial conc.	Equil. conc.	x/m .	Log c .	Log x/m .
20'00	8'20	11'80	0'9138	1'0719	20'13	8'00	12'13	0'9031	1'0838	20'05	7'83	12'22	0'8938	1'0871
17'00	7'00	10'00	0'8451	1'0000	17'00	6'70	10'30	0'8261	1'0128	15'20	5'39	9'81	0'7316	0'9917
10'93	4'53	6'40	0'6561	0'8062	10'60	4'00	6'60	0'6021	0'8195	10'22	3'22	7'00	0'5079	0'8451
6'66	2'80	3'86	0'4472	0'5866	6'66	2'33	4'33	0'3674	0'6365	6'66	1'94	4'72	0'2878	0'6739
5'00	2'13	2'87	0'3284	0'4579	4'90	1'60	3'30	0'2041	0'5185	5'00	1'33	3'67	0'1239	0'5647
Galactose.					Lactulose.					Mannose.				
20'05	7'22	12'83	0'8585	1'1082	20'11	8'11	12'00	0'9090	1'0792	20'05	6'88	13'17	0'8376	1'1200
15'90	5'41	10'49	0'7332	1'0207	16'03	6'01	10'02	0'7789	1'0008	17'40	5'72	11'68	0'7574	1'0675
10'28	2'83	7'45	0'4518	0'8722	10'22	3'22	7'00	0'5079	0'8451	10'17	2'83	7'34	0'4518	0'8657
6'66	1'61	5'05	0'2068	0'7033	6'72	1'94	4'78	0'2878	0'6794	6'66	2'00	4'66	0'3010	0'6684
5'00	1'33	3'67	0'1239	0'5647	5'00	1'33	3'66	0'1239	0'5635	5'00	1'33	3'66	0'1239	0'5635
Rhamnose.					Sucrose.					Maltose.				
20'00	4'16	15'84	0'6191	1'1998	5'00	0'32	4'68	-0'4949	0'6702	5'00	0'24	4'76	-0'6198	0'6776
15'62	3'22	12'40	0'5079	1'0934	6'66	0'35	6'31	-0'4559	0'8000	6'66	0'29	6'37	-0'5376	0'8041
9'94	2'07	7'87	0'3160	0'8960	9'99	0'71	9'28	-0'1487	0'9675	10'00	0'59	9'41	-0'2291	0'9736
6'65	1'22	5'43	0'0854	0'7348	14'22	1'22	13'00	0'0864	1'1139	14'13	1'11	13'02	0'0453	1'1145
5'00	0'85	4'15	0'0706	0'6180	19'47	2'44	17'03	0'3874	1'2311	19'50	2'43	17'07	0'3856	1'2321

TABLE II

Carbohydrates.	Initial conc.	Equil. conc.	% Adsorption.
Dextrin	0'0250	0'0018	92'8
Inulin	0'0250	0'0024	90'4
Maltin	0'0250	0'0000	100'0
Starch	0'0250	0'0008	96'8
<i>a</i> -Methyl <i>d</i> -glucoside	0'0250	0'0026	89'6
Raffinose	0'0446	0'0006	98'7

DISCUSSION

An examination of the data clearly shows that active charcoal has considerable adsorptive power for the different sugars. Measurements showed that the adsorption of the various sugars on silica gel was generally less than 2%, which was negligible compared to the 55 to 95% adsorption shown by charcoal. In this respect the behaviour of the two adsorbents are quite different.

Fig 1. shows the plots of x/m against equilibrium concentrations for the different sugars. The isotherms thus obtained are located in a regular order. Thus at the bottom of the figure we have the two pentoses, arabinose and xylose, having adsorption coefficients of about 57% and 66% respectively. Proceeding upwards we come across the hexoses, dextrose, fructose, mannose and galactose, which all lie close together in a bunch. The adsorption coefficients of the hexoses lie between 70 to 75%. The isotherms of the pair of bioses lie at the top and run close to one another. The adsorption coefficients of the bioses are distinctly higher and have a value approximating 88%. The methyl pentose, rhamnose, with an adsorption coefficient of

80% comes midway between the hexoses and the bioses. Two regular features emerge from the above data. Firstly the adsorption increases in a general way with increasing molecular weight of the solute. Secondly sugars of the same family form distinct groups of adsorption isotherms. The adsorption coefficients of the various sugars of the same family lie close together and increase in regular steps as one passes from the pentoses to the bioses.

The behaviour of rhamnose is somewhat anomalous. It may be regarded either as a methyl pentose or a reduced hexose. Although its molecular weight (164) is less than that of the hexoses (180), it shows a larger adsorption. Further the isotherm for rhamnose differs from those of the hexoses which have a characteristic concave form, but is more akin to the isotherms of the pentoses which are more or less rectilinear over the concentrations studied. Though similar in form, the isotherm for rhamnose differs from those of the pentoses in as much as it is located much higher than any of the pentoses.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

[A=arabinose; X=xylose; D=dextrose;
F=fructose; G=galactose; M=mannose;
R=rhamnose; S=sucrose; m=maltose]

In Fig. 2, the plot of $\log x/m$ against $\log c$ have been given. The plots are all straight lines which shows that the usual adsorption equation $x/m = \alpha c^{1/n}$ is generally obeyed. From Fig. 2, the values of α and $1/n$ have been calculated in the usual manner, and are given in Table III. A comparison of these values again clearly brings out the family relationship of the sugars with regard to adsorption.

TABLE III

Substance	Arabinose	Xylose	Dextrose	Galactose	Mannose	Fructose	Rhamnose	Maltose	Sucrose
$1/n$... 1'054	0'820	0'652	0'613	0'641	0'531	0'870	0'605	0'605
α	... 1'288	2'188	3'166	3'758	3'758	3'802	4'467	12'30	12'30
Melting point	... 159°	144°	146°	166°	195°	95°	93°	110°	165
Period of osazone formation (min.)	10	7	5	15 to 19	1½	2	9	...	30
No of hydrates	... Nil	Nil	one	Nil	Nil	Nil	one	one	one

The pentoses including rhamnose have values of $1/n$ approximating 1. The hexoses have almost a constant value with a mean of 0.635, whilst the bioses have a mean value of 0.605. It is interesting to note that fructose, the only keto-hexose studied, has a somewhat lower value of 0.531. The value of α increases in a general way with increasing molecular weight of the sugar.

The adsorption of a number of polysaccharides is given in Table II. It will be seen that the adsorption coefficients are all high and conform to the general rule that adsorption increases with increasing complexity (*cf.* Rosenthaler, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1907, 244, 259; Michaelis and Rona *loc. cit.*).

The adsorption of α -methyl *D*-glucoside (89.6%) may be compared with that of glucose (64%) at about the same concentration and also of the tri-saccharide raffinose (98.7%) with the bioses (about 94%), further confirming the above rule.

In Table III, the melting points, the period of formation of osazone (Mulliken, "Identification of Pure Organic Compounds," Vol. I, pp. 29-30) and the existence of hydrates where they occur, have been recorded. It will be seen that there is no simple relationship between melting point and constitution of the sugar. Linner and Gortner (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1935, 39, 35) observed during the adsorption of saturated fatty acids on charcoal a parallel fluctuation of adsorption and melting point with odd and even members of the series. On this basis they pointed out that the adsorbed molecules may be in a solid state *i.e.* a sort of crystallisation may take place on the surface. In the present experiments no such behaviour has been observed.

The period of formation of osazones vary with the constitution of sugars but beyond a very general connection no rigid regularity can be observed. The formation of hydrates appears to be quite a specific property of the sugars. It is thus remarkable that in spite of the lack of any regularity between the physical and chemical properties of the sugars and their constitution, the adsorption data should have a neat family relationship. One may therefore conclude that although chemical constitution does play a part in the process of adsorption, the resulting attachment between the adsorbent and the solute is not so intimate as to be affected by the detailed structure of the molecule. In other words the attachment must be even looser than in compounds such as hydrates. Further work is in progress.

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